

Bhattacharya alkali test of rice

dish, and 2) that the number of grains per dish should be such as to leave a minimum mean space of 5–6 cm²/grain. Once these conditions are met (it is immaterial if the limits are slightly exceeded), the volume of alkali per grain can be ignored. We have been using reference method II in our routine work. However, alternative VIII might be optimal, because it is closest to the original Little et al method (I) while allowing sufficient space for maximum kernel spreading. ■

Individuals, organizations, and media are invited to quote or reprint articles or excerpts from articles in the IRRN. Duplicate prints of photos and illustrations are available to media on request from the Office of Information Services, IRRI. Persons who wish additional details of information presented in IRRN should write directly to the authors.

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Varietal reaction to the kresek phase of bacterial blight

P. Ranga Reddy and Susanta K. Mohanty, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack 753006, India

Bacterial blight of rice caused by *Xanthomonas oryzae* exhibits two distinct types of symptoms: leaf blight and kresek or wilt. Leaf blight occurs in almost all of rice-growing India. Kresek is occasionally observed in experimental plots and in farmers' fields, particularly in isolated patches. Although kresek is more severe than leaf blight, information on it is limited. Therefore a study was initiated to artificially induce the disease and investigate the susceptibility of some popular rice varieties.

The roots of 15-day-old TN1 seedlings were washed thoroughly. The root tips were finely trimmed with scissors and dipped for 30 minutes in a 48-hour-old bacterial suspension (about 10⁹ cells/ml) grown on potato sucrose agar medium. The treated seedlings were transplanted in pots. Wilting symptoms began to appear 10 days after inoculation and continued appearing up to 20 days, by which time the maximum number of seedlings had collapsed. But not all the inoculated seedlings exhibited kresek; some surviving plants exhibited leaf blight symptoms. Bacteria reisolated from the wilted leaves were confirmed to be *X. oryzae* on the basis of physiological characters and

Reaction of some rice varieties to kresek. Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, India.

Varieties	Wilted plants (%)
Lacrosse Zenith/Nira, Nagarbhog	0
BJ1, CO13, Krishna, Zukkoku, Sachikaze, Chinsurah Boro II, Raminad Str. 3, Kanto 51	2.0-8.5
TN1, Jamuna, Malagkit Sungsong, NP125, Cauvery, Kalinga I, Kalinga II, TKM6, Padma	10.0-18.5
IR8, Sigadis, Zenith, IR30, NC128I, Sona, Karuna, IR22, Katna, Kanchi, Rajeswari	22.0-38.5
Pusa 2-21, SLO 16, Jagannath, MTU 17, Supriya, IR24, Semora mangga, Pankaj, Sakti, Vijaya, Jaya	40.0-92.0

pathogenicity on rice plants.

Sixty-four indica and japonica varieties were inoculated using the above method. Ninety-two percent of the plants of the variety Jaya wilted, and 70% of Tadukan and Vijaya plants died. The varieties Lacrosse Zenith/Nira and Nagarbhog showed no wilting symptoms, indicating high kresek resistance. Wilting was minimal (2-6%) in BJ1, Chinsurah Boro II, Krishna, and Zukkoku. But TN1, which is highly susceptible to leaf blight, has only 12% wilting (see table). That indicates that the varietal reaction to the leaf blight phase is not similar to that to the kresek phase. ■

Resistance to sheath blight disease in India

S. Manian and K. Manibhushan Rao, Centre for Advanced Studies in Botany, University of Madras, Madras 600005, India

One hundred and thirty-four entries from the International Rice Sheath Blight Nursery (IRSHBN), 30 cultures from the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project (AICRIP) program, Hyderabad, and 6 entries from local collections were tested for resistance to sheath blight from March to July 1978 at the Maduravoil Field Research Laboratory, University of Madras, Madras, India. Checks were the resistant IR20, the moderately resistant IR1487-194-5-3-2, and the susceptible Pankaj. The inoculum was autoclaved rice stem cuttings (about 3–4 cm) with 5% dextrose, inoculated with a virulent isolate of *Corticium sasakii* and incubated for 15 days. Among the methods tried, the stem-tape inoculation technique was the most efficient for artificial inoculation. The sheaths of 90-day-old plants were inoculated 5 cm above the water level. They were scored for reaction 12 days later when the disease intensity was maximum in most cultivars.

The following entries were rated as highly resistant and resistant.

Highly resistant: BR4-30-51-2, BR51-49-6, IR2796-44-2, ARC 5925, and ARC 5943.

Resistant: B1757d-Sm-6-1, B1757d-Sm-47-1, B1757d-Sm-47-3, B1757d-Sm-47-6, B1757d-Sm-50-6, B2012d-SM-52-1-2, BR51-26-10, BRS1-95-2, BR51-196-2, BR52-85-7, IET4154 (CR44-121-1), IET4834 (CR117-1), IET 5126 (RP661-12-4-4-2), IR20, IR532-1-18(S), IR203.5-244-3-2-3,

IR2053-200-4, IR2070-132-2-2-5, IR2070-747-6-3-2-1 (IR32), IR2071-588-4-4, IR2071-803-5-2-6, IR2071-843-1-1-6, IR2328-198-1-1-1, IR2793-97-3-2, IR2798-115-2-3, IR2817-117-2-1, IR2832-172-6-2, OR4422-98-3-6, IR4531-10057-5-1-1, IR4531-10057-5-1-2, A 15-100-1-3-1,

ARC 10618, ARC 10836, DA 29, IR2071-648-4-4-6, IR3464-149-3-2, IR4641-143-1, Nizersail, Rajasail, Tabend, Ta-poo-cho-z, ARC 14342, ARC 14529, ARC 10572, TKM6, and Kattichamba. ■

Donors of bacterial blight resistance

C. L. Raina, Ish Kumar, S. S. Saini, and G. S. Sidhu, Punjab Agricultural University, Regional Rice Research Station, Kapurthala 144601, India

In 1978 kharif we screened 885 lines from our germplasm collection for bacterial blight resistance at the Kapurthala station. Ten plants of each line were inoculated with a pure culture of *Xanthomonas oryzae* by the clipping method, and scored 15 days later. Seventeen lines were found resistant (score of 3 on the Standard Evaluation

Distribution of scores of resistance donors of bacterial blight inoculated artificially at the Regional Rice Research Station, Kapurthala, Punjab, India.

Score ^a	Leaf area infested (%)	Collections	
		No.	%
1	1	0	0.0
3	1-5	17	1.9
5	5-25	360	40.7
7	25-50	456	51.5
9	50	52	5.9

^aStandard Evaluation System scale.

System scale): Norin 18, Hokkaido, Tainan 3, Taichung 65, IR878B-45-1, IR9880, IR1712-166-1, IR1634-520-1-2, IR1614-605-3-4, Zinnya 31, CK10-152, Norin 18-LC-5, OR45-61-23, A/R-248,

CP231, Chung-Lin-Chun, and Kachamota. Those lines are being used as resistance donors in the breeding program.

Of the others, 360 were scored 5; 456, 7; and 52, 9 (see table). ■

Suggested revision of scoring system for rice sheath rot disease

K. Satyanarayana and C. Sadasiva Reddy, All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, Hyderabad 500030, India

Many commercial varieties in the intensive rice-growing areas of India, especially in the rabi or late kharif crop, are susceptible to sheath rot disease caused by *Acrocyndrium oryzae*. To incorporate a high degree of resistance into high-yielding varieties, scientists need a systematic approach with a standard scale to screen germplasm and determine resistant genotypes.

The Standard Evaluation System designed by IRRI does not adequately identify resistant donors because the scale is based on the percentage of tillers affected. That gives insufficient information on resistance or susceptibility because if all tillers in a clump are infected to a low degree, we grade that genotype as "9" — regardless of panicle damage. Furthermore, the percentage of affected tillers shows the prevalence of the disease — not its severity.

A scale showing the coverage of lesions on the sheath and their effect on the emerging panicle would more

appropriately identify the resistant lines.

We suggest the scale given in the figure. ■